

Semi-Automatic Tool to Count Mosquito Eggs in Ovitrap Stick Images

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Plan

1. Introduction
2. Methodology
3. Image Processing & Graphical User Interface (GUI)
4. Tests
5. Conclusions

1. Introduction

Aedes aegypti mosquito is a sanitary threat

Virus vector: dengue, zika, chikungunya, yellow fever

→ When and Where are outbreaks

Aedes aegypti (from Wikipedia)

Some cities are applying a monitoring solution

Ovitrap: a wooden stick in a cup with water

Mosquito females lay eggs close to water level

An operator count eggs behind a magnifier

error prone and time consuming

Gulich Institute was asked to automate egg counting

150 ovitrap sites selected in Cordoba, Argentina

Counted every week, up to several hundreds eggs per ovitrap

2. Methodology

Stick images were shot by a cellular phone (typ. 12 Mpix)
With sharpness, uniform background, controlled illumination

Image Processing

Detect the stick and dark blobs
User interface to refine detection

Three main challenges

Time: 4 weeks for development

Visibility: Eggs are small (typ 12..20 pix)

Dirty parts (insects, excrements)

Varying background (wood)

Counting: some eggs are grouped into clusters (blob)

2. Methodology

Existing work

EggCounter (2012): adaptable thresh; blob count can be edited

Icount (2016): adaptable thresh

Difference with existing works

Further reduce human intervention:

- A focusing technique to restrict egg search to the stick
- A multi-threshold procedure to get a confidence in the count

Manual adjustment (focusing and threshold)

- For refinement
- As a fallback if bad automatic processing

3. Image Processing and GUI

A) Image Processing (with *openCV* library)

- (3.1) To get a stick Bounding Box
- (3.2) To detect the dark blobs (egg or egg clusters)
- (3.3) To count the eggs in blobs
- (3.4) To estimate the total count by threshold selection

B) Graphical User Interface (with *Qt* library) (3.5)

- To show (and refine) the stick Bounding Box
- To show the total count profile versus threshold
- To display (and edit) the egg count by blob on the image

Multi platform: Python 3.5 openCV4.2 PyQt5

3. Image Processing and GUI

3.1 Stick Bounding Box

Filter image with `cv2.inrange()` in **HSV color space**

Sticks are mainly red, quite pale and bright

Hue:[-30..30] Saturation:[30..120] Value:[100..255]

Largest contour normally contains the stick

Extract the **Bounding Box**

Possible manual refinement

Added value

Bounding Box avoids false counts out of stick

Bounding Box speeds up processing of the next steps

The known stick width (20 mm) offers a pixel size

3. Image Processing and GUI

3.2 Object Detection

Thresholding + Find contours + size filtering

- cv2.threshold() with low values (eggs are dark)
- Contours from cv2.findContours() are fitted to ellipses
cv2.fitEllipse() → ctrX, ctrY, a, b (semi axes, b > a)
Reject small objects: $2*b < 0.3$ mm (in pix)
- Area of blobs contour (cv2.contourArea())
1EggArea: Median area for contours with length in [0.4..0.8]mm
Hypothesis: Isolated eggs are present on the sticks

3. Image Processing and GUI

3.3 Counting Eggs

Contour egg count = round (contourArea / **1EggArea**)

Empirical reduction if count > 5: count = round(0.85*count)

Cluster area often overestimated due to shadow between eggs

If count > 25, cluster is expected to be erroneous

3. Image Processing and GUI

3.4 Threshold Selection

A stick count = Sum of contour egg counts

A profile of counts versus threshold: a plateau is desired

Minimal count variance for thresholds [Thr-7 .. Thr+7]

Center of plateau is returned as optimal thres

Result = median count around optimal thres

4. Tests and Results

The system was tested on different imagery

- ICount images

- Stick images from different cameras

- Limited tests due to Covid

4. Tests and Results

4.1 « ICount » imagery (eggs are 25 pixel long)

4. Tests and Results

4.3 Cordoba, difficult case (non uniform stick, dirty parts)

4. Tests and Results

4.3 Cordoba, difficult case: limiting Bounding Box

4. Tests and Results

Automatic count reliability depends on

- Background quality (wood)

- Presence of outliers (non-egg dark objects)

- Image quality and egg size ←

Image capture is crucial

- Sharpness, Contrast, Uniform Background

- Egg size (better if > 20 pixel)

Profile and count in less than 1 second

- But manual refinement may last

Optimal threshold tends to be similar

- For a given acquisition setup

5. Conclusions

- Development of automatic counting of eggs
 - Automatic Bounding Box on stick
 - Automatic threshold based on count stability
- Control or refinement with the Graphical Interface
 - To refine the Bounding Box
 - To refine threshold
 - To check / edit counts of individual blobs
- Image capture is crucial
 - Image quality
 - Egg size